

**SIGNIFICANCES IN PROMOTING COMPROMISE BEHAVIOUR AMONG
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Alagappa University, Karaikudi- Tamil Nadu**Dr. P. PAUL DEVANESAN**Professor of Education, Director, CD Cell,
Alagappa University, Karaikudi- Tamil Nadu**Abstract**

In the present context, Teacher and Teacher Educator face many problems in their working Institutions because of these problem, they face unfavorable environment, non- cooperative tendency among co-teacher and student's. This kind of Problems may create dissonance situation in their professional Institute. In this Juncture, the teacher Educators should change their pattern of behaviour. Particularly the compromise behaviour in one of the most important behaviour to change their unfavorable environment to favorable environment. The main purpose of developing compromise is to fulfill needs of present situation in the changing the society and to create good students and Student-Teachers by giving training through Guidance and Counseling Practices to cope up with the problems existing in the society. The significance of the article is to emphases the development of the potentialities of the students at maximum level by the teacher educators to promote their own academic benefits and for the welfare of future nation.

Key Words: *Teacher educator, Dissonance, Compromise behaviour, Professional environment and Consonance.*

i) Compromise Behaviour: Introduction

In the Prevailing Professional Environment, Teacher Educators face many problems. These problems arise because of the unfavorable professional environment, non-cooperative tendency of co-teachers and students and they may create dissonance situation in their professional environment. If Teacher Educators want to survive in a congenial professional environment, they must change their pattern of behaviour. Particularly the compromise behaviour is one of the most important behaviour to change their unfavorable environment into favorable environment. In other words, the inconsistent attitudes change into consistent by preferring positive cognitive elements. This type of behaviour pattern develop human relationship with their co-worker, students and administrators and also ultimately it promotes mental satisfaction. Therefore, the compromise behaviour is a more suitable behaviour to maintain good mental health and among Teacher Educators infact it creates consonance situation to attain the high level of academic development and achievement.

ii) Statement of the thematic topic

One of the important adjustive behaviour is the compromise behaviour which is needed to be developed among each and every teacher educators because this kind of behaviour makes

teacher educator to realize their introspective process and understand his state even when he is emotional state. These kinds of feeling also make other person to realize his own inner deeds. In this juncture, when teacher educators come forwarded to confer their inner realities, then they will make the environment congenial and the happenings that are going on will be congenial. So this is the brief explanation reveals the meaning of the topic

iii) Limitation of the present thematic topic

This topic has its own primary important in the training centre of various college of education. The teacher educators are the persons who give training to the students to promote their compromise behaviour. This Kind of behaviour creates a boundary to develop human relations and professional sprit. These advantages are very essential to make all the college of education in rural and urban areas run the college peacefully. Particularly teacher educators working in training colleges must develop their behaviour which will helps them to have more involvement in their training activities to create a value based good teacher.

ii) The Conceptual Composition of Compromise behaviour

The conceptual composition of compromise behaviour comprises of many concepts. which are needed one to create a favorable professional environment in almost all Educational Training Institutions. In any educational Training Institution, the teacher Educators should have constant interaction with their fellow teachers and students to share their idea each other and at the same time it should be accepted by all. The accomplishment of the teachers in any Educational Training Institution is mainly based on favorable professional environment to perform their work in an effective way. In the most of educational institutions, the teacher educators deviated from the situation because the situation is not in favour of them. In this circumstance, the Compromise behaviour is a needed one to chance the situation in favour of them to diminish the mal- adjustive behaviour.

In the working environment the teacher educators accept others ideas and concepts of fellow teachers educators in a reciprocal way. This kind of attitude shows their compromise nature between teachers Educators in their professional environment. If teacher educators want to improve their teaching – learning process in a effective manner by making use of ability and skill based on the students capacity and their nature may lead to have safe performance. At the same time, their compromise behaviour is a need based one in the present scenario to strengthen the quality of Teacher Education, in professional Institutions. So, the above concepts are considered as an essential one to promote quality teacher Education through compromise behaviour.

iii) Essentials of Compromise behaviour

The compromise behaviour is considered as an essential behaviour and it is need for all teacher educators to enhance their academic activity without facing any conflict in professional Environment. Particularly, the teacher Educators working in colleges of Education should have this kind of behaviour for promoting his training skill for the student teachers to involve effectively in teaching process and it promotes students performance based on his ability and skills. At the same time, teacher Educators can develop good human relationship with their co-workers and Students. This kind of behaviour is an essential one to create a favorable teaching – learning environment and it creates job satisfaction on the part of the teachers educators and learners.

Even if teacher educator face conflict situation, the compromise behaviour will change the situation by reducing the painful feeling caused by frustration and also the teachers themselves promote compromise behaviour that may develop the problem solving skills among Teacher Educators by selecting appropriate solution for any problems related to academic activities. In this way, the compromise behaviour creates a consonance situation. Further, the behaviour is also useful to make use of manpower to promote academic outcomes.

iv) Psychological and sociological perspectives of compromise behaviour

Psychology is the science of behaviour. Therefore, the compromise behaviour is one of the important psychological behaviour in the field of behavioral psychology. It attempts to understand, to control and to explain the dynamics of complex interpersonal human behaviour. It also enables teachers educators to improve the capacity of understanding by which teacher educators can meet any challenging situation. Though the process of compromise behaviour is a need based one to improve academic environment in a congenial way, Now-a days the teacher Educators are facing emotional problems in their working environment because of their mental conflict, which is occur due to the non-sharing of the work with fellow teachers and accumulation of work on teachers Educators allotted by the higher authority. In these circumstances, the teacher Educators need to change the pattern of behaviour particularly, they should develop compromise behaviour to sustain in the environment and promote congenial professional environment.

The compromise behaviour of teacher is an essential one for Teaching-Learning process in classroom situation through which the students Teachers maintain Teacher –Student relationship and the same may be improved. Therefore, the psychological aspect of compromise behaviour reveals that teacher - student adjustment in the Training Institutional school-related activities.

The compromise behaviour of teacher educators is an essential one. Because of this behaviour, the holistic personality is developed among Students. The holistic personality is developed, because the compromise behaviour is making pleasant experiences by having individual introspection. These experiences are important to have pleasant experiences among leaners. Because, the experiences of Positive imprints crystallize to form holistic and dynamic personality. Therefore, the compromise behaviour of teachers is one of the important aspects in developing dynamic personality among children.

In the sociological point of view; the compromise behaviour focuses on individuals' adjustive capacity to meet and cope with stressful situation. Therefore, the compromise behaviour is a needed in the present scenario for the fast changing society to create good student teachers by giving training through Guidance and Counseling practices to cope with the problems existing in the society. In this circumstance, teacher Educators should develop his potentialities of the Student Teachers at maximum level for his own academic benefits and for the welfare of students learning.

v) Role of Compromise behaviour in developing congenial atmosphere in Teacher Educational Institutions:

The Quality of Teacher Education is mainly based on the congenial Environment of the institution. Particularly, this kind of environment is created based on teachers' compromise behaviour.

- I. The compromise behaviour promotes co-operative tendency, which is useful to resolve the conflict in professional environment.

- II. The nature of compromise behaviour makes teacher involve openly in the academic related activities in a co-operative manner. So the relationship among teachers and commitment to the organization will be promoted and strengthened (Tjosvold et.al 2001)
- III. The teachers educators compromise behaviour makes Student Teachers easily understand the feeling of co-worker and Students. so that the situation may be converted into congenial one to interact with them easily.
- IV. Through Compromise behaviour, Teachers Educators may promote the skill of problem solving. The problem related to Administration, Academic activities, Teachers activities, Students and workers may be solved and the Institutional environment will be a conflict free environment.
- V. Compromise behaviour promote the habit of mutual understanding with fellow teachers educators in the professional environment -Once the habit formation related to adjustive behaviour is their in educational institutions it will be very helpful to attain the expected goal and promote mutual benefits among Teachers Educators and others working in Educational Institution.

vi) Compromise behaviour and Problem Solving skill:

The Teacher Educator's compromise behaviour is first of all reduce the painful feelings which is caused by frustration. Now a day the teacher are facing many problems in their working environment, due to the Non-Cooperative tendency with Co-Teachers and Students. In this situation, the teacher Educators may perform compromise behaviour and apply coping strategy to understand the nature of the problem, intensity of problem and solve the same by identifying and selecting appropriate positive cognitive elements to solve the problems and this kind of activity pave a ways to create congenial atmosphere in the professional environment and direct and guide the Teacher Educators to utilize the skills, abilities, and knowledge in a rational and meaningful way to improve the activities related to Quality Education.

vii) Promoting Compromise behaviour:

In working environment, the teachers compromise behaviour is promoted by few influencing factors. These factors are discussed below in detailed manner:

- I. Emotional balance plays a vital role in developing compromise behaviour among Teacher Educators.
- II. If teacher Educators have well physical and mental health it develops harmonious relationship and it is considered as a base for promoting compromise behaviour among them.
- III. Make use of Skills, abilities and involvement of work are considered as important factors for developing compromise behaviour.
- IV. The Teacher Educators change his direction of efforts by changing the original goals.
 - V. The teacher educators may satisfy himself by using an apparent substitute for the real thing.
 - VI. The teacher educators adopt themselves to attain the harmony by making use of his intelligence for proper choice and decisions particularly when they face conflict situation and stressful moments.

viii) Conclusion

Compromise behaviour is one of the most common and effective way of coping behaviour to resolve the conflict and frustration in an professional environment. Particularly, teachers who are working in colleges of Education face conflict situation. In this Juncture, this kind of behaviour may prevent non-cooperative tendency of co-worker, students and administrator, problem related to salary and student's, parochialism. If Teacher Educators want to minimize the above problems in Educational Training Institutions to cope with situation, the teacher Educators should have compromise behaviour and it must be improved in their working environment by establishing a true, good rapport with all. So that they can workS effectively and efficiently.

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